

PARKING SPACE MANAGEMENT FOR TRUCKS

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Globalization is significantly increasing the flow of global cargo, which must be carried out through large shipping, gateway ports. Often, the focus of expanding port capacity to handle future cargo flows is to improve terminal efficiency, but investment in critical port infrastructure is just as crucial. Blockages at ports can be avoided only if fast and trouble-free transportation of goods to the hinterland is guaranteed [1-6].

Taking into account that the main part of cargo transportation in the countries of Central Asia is delivered by road transport, the territory of the Republic of Uzbekistan is a convenient transit country (see Figure 1). At the same time, it is necessary to ensure all security for vehicles transiting through the territory of the Republic [10].

Figure 1. TRSECA-TRANSPORT CORRIDOR

Traffic safety includes the following components:

- traffic safety (TS);
- environmental safety;
- personal safety of moving vehicles and drivers of transported goods;
- organizing the work of drivers in compliance with traffic safety requirements;
- compliance of drivers with regulatory requirements in work mode;
- organization of medical examination of drivers before the flight (and after the flight);
- creating conditions for improving the skills of drivers and ATK specialists. After getting a driver's license, drivers must undergo training and practice every year. Even if there is a break in the practice of driving a car for more than one year, it also happens when switching from one direction (route) to another or from one type of transport to another [6];
- Analysis of accidents and violations of traffic rules (including motor vehicles); in this regard, study and take into account the accident;
- ensuring that the technical condition of moving vehicles meets the requirements of road safety;

In order to ensure the above safety, it is very necessary to build and equip roads of international importance according to the standards that meet the current requirements [9].

In addition, it is predicted that the throughput of agricultural and manufacturing products will increase significantly in the next ten years. Local authorities should improve the efficiency of existing infrastructure to prevent traffic congestion in the border area. An important part of the necessary infrastructure is the availability of sufficient parking spaces for trucks (see Figure 2) [8].

Figure 2. Safe parking places for trucks

World experience. In order to solve these problems, taking into account the large amount of cargo collected in sea transport, the Port Authority of Hamburg implemented the project "Management of Parking Spaces". The main objective is to improve the efficiency of various parking areas in the port area by using telematics support. Improving the transparency of existing parking spaces and implementing the PreGate parking pilot project will improve traffic flow and freight, reduce traffic-related "pollution" and improve road safety in the future. The following case study exemplifies the approach, planning and implementation of this project. In addition, it describes funding opportunities, current legislation and other similar projects [7].

Things to be done in Uzbekistan and Central Asia.

European ports are important gateways connecting European industrial clusters with the rest of the world through transport corridors. About 74% of goods entering or leaving Europe go by sea, and Europe has some of the best port facilities in the world. In addition to the economic benefits, the increasing importance of the infrastructure of ports faces challenges related to internal traffic, traffic growth and investment. Therefore, in the EU 2020 strategy, the European Commission plans to support the smart and sustainable growth of the economy and related infrastructure. One of the main concerns here is to overcome bottlenecks within the infrastructure and especially in the TEN-T and TRASECA corridors. In addition, the White Paper on transport emphasizes the importance of ports and their important hinterland connectivity, which shows that not only the transport of goods but also the related infrastructures are in focus [6].

In 2013, 9,700 ocean-going vessels carrying large-volume container cargo were called to the port of Hamburg. These vessels brought a capacity of 9.3 million TEU to the port. Of these, 59 percent, i.e. 5.4 million, are intended for the hinterland of the Port of Hamburg (Port of Hamburg Marketing, 2014a). A study based on 2013 estimated a future capacity of 16 million TEUs in 2030.

Long queues of international trucks moving along these corridors at the border post services are the main problem of today's landlocked countries. By reducing truck idle time in queues, both environmental and economic benefits will be achieved for our society [5]. It is necessary to organize safe parking places for trucks based on the AETR agreement in the territory of each country (Central Asian countries). In this way, road traffic accidents will be prevented. Taking into account that more than 80% of the volume of international cargo transportation of Central Asian countries is carried by trucks, it is necessary to

organize safe parking places for each transiting country approximately every 50-60 km.[4]. The number of transit routes in our republic is 99. These directions are connected by 35 highways. The total length of these highways is 4325 km. This shows that the government should organize safe parking spaces accordingly [2-3].

Through this, the achievements of our Republic will be: fully complying with the AETR agreement;

- Transit increases the attractiveness of moving international freight cars;
- Economic growth is observed;
- Liability for material liability in international transport is drastically reduced [1].

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